

ROLE OF PRE-SOWING TREATMENTS IN BREAKING DORMANCY AND IMPROVING GERMINATION OF *Pterocarpus santalinus* L. SEEDS

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Abstract

Pterocarpus santalinus L., widely recognized as the "State Tree of Andhra Pradesh" and the "Lal Chandan" is an endangered and endemic species native to the Southern regions of the Eastern Ghats. Its seeds are characterized by a hard, impermeable seed coat, while offering physical protection to the embryo; also obstruct germination, primarily due to the presence of phenolic compounds that inhibit germinative activity. The present study evaluated the efficacy of twelve pre-sowing treatments, including chemical, organic, and mechanical methods on the seed germination of *P. santalinus* seeds. Among the treatments, T3 (soaking seeds in GA₃ @300 ppm for 24 hours) yielded the most favorable results, exhibiting the minimum germination time (22.67 days) and the highest germination percentage (71.67%), followed by T2 (GA₃ @200 ppm for 24 hours). In contrast, T12 (untreated seeds) showed significantly lower germination percentages, emphasizing the importance of appropriate pre-sowing treatments to enhance germination in *P. santalinus*.

Keywords: emergence, germination, impermeable, phenolic compounds, pre-sowing

Introduction

Pterocarpus santalinus is a small to medium-sized tree in the Fabaceae family that is most widely known as red sandalwood in English and Rakta Chandana in Sanskrit. The term "*Pterocarpus*" is derived from Greek words "pteron" (wing), "Karpos" (fruit), which describes a plant that possesses characteristics similar to those of *Santalum album* L., Indian sandalwood. It is extensively found in tropical regions of the world, particularly in India, Sri Lanka, Taiwan and China (Dhanabal *et al.*, 2007). It is an endangered and endemic tree found in Southern portions of the Eastern Ghats of India (Ahmed and Nayer, 1984; Jadav *et al.*, 2001). In India, the natural range of *P. santalinus* used to be a very restricted in an area of 15,540 km² in the Southeast (Sarma, 1993). *Red sander* is a strong light demander and cannot withstand water-logged conditions. The leaves are trifoliate and alternating, measuring 3-9 cm long. The leaves fall starts from Jan to mid-March. The flowers are yellow, densely arranged in simple or sparingly branched racemes. Flowering occurs from February to April, soon after new leaves come in April and continue till mid-May. The fruits are 6-9 cm long pods that formed rapidly but get ripened in next February-March. After eleven months of flowering, the matured reddish brown winged pods are formed with one or two seeds in it which are more or less kidney shaped. Pods have an irregular orbicular shape, are 3-4 cm in diameter including the wing (Dayanand, 1988 and Shambharkar, 2022). Owing

to heavy exploitation from its valuable wood and essential oil, the species is currently classified as endangered on the IUCN Red Data List. In order to meet the growing demand for *P. santalinus* wood while preserving the remaining natural populations, efforts must be made to construct sustainable plantations of the species (Naidu *et al.*, 2001). *P. santalinus* L. having hard seed coat, poor viability and sensitivity to temperature shows relatively low germination rate when not treated properly before sowing. Due to the absence of pre sowing treatments to the seed makes it difficult for the seed to germinate (Kalimuthu and Lakshmanan, 1995). The overexploitation and loss of habitat have led to the listing of *P. santalinus* as an endangered species. To ensure its survival, effective conservation strategies can be developed with an understanding of its germination process (Dayanand and Lohidas, 1988).

Materials And Methods

The experiment was carried out during 2024-25 at Department of Forestry, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. PDKV, Akola. Seeds of *P. santalinus* were collected from Andhra Pradesh. Before sowing of seeds, the Polybags having 200-gauge thickness were used and filled with the common media comprising of soil + sand + FYM in the ratio 2:1:1. The experiment was laid out in a Randomised Block Design (RBD) with twelve treatments and three replications. The treatments details are as follows.

Treatment	Details of Treatment
T ₁	Seeds soaking with 100 ppm GA ₃ for 24 hours
T ₂	Seeds soaking with 200 ppm GA ₃ for 24 hours
T ₃	Seeds soaking with 300 ppm GA ₃ for 24 hours
T ₄	Seeds soaking with 1% H ₂ SO ₄ for 20 minutes
T ₅	Seeds soaking with 3% H ₂ SO ₄ for 20 minutes
T ₆	Seeds soaking with 5% H ₂ SO ₄ for 20 minutes
T ₇	Seeds soaking with 1% HCl for 20 minutes
T ₈	Seeds soaking with 3% HCl for 20 minutes
T ₉	Seeds soaking with 5% HCl for 20 minutes
T ₁₀	Seeds soaking with Cow dung slurry (1:1) for 48 hours
T ₁₁	Separating seeds from pods with a sharp knife or scalpel and sown directly
T ₁₂	Control (untreated seeds)

The treatments were observed once in two days for recording the observations since the date of sowing, and noted days to emergence, days for germination and percent of germination, were taken for the last seedling emergence were recorded. The germination percentage was calculated as the percent of germinating seeds starting from the first germination to no further germination. It was calculated by given formula

$$\text{Germination Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of seed germinated}}{\text{Total No. of seed sown}} \times 100$$

The observations were recorded and get analyzed with the statistical tool of "OPSTAT computer program", the results and interference were drawn and presented.

Result And Discussion

From the data presented in table 1, it revealed the results pertaining to key germination parameters, namely days to emergence, days to final germination, and germination percentage. The data clearly indicate

significant differences among the twelve pre-sowing treatments applied to *Pterocarpus santalinus* seeds.

From table-1, regarding days to emergence in *P. santalinus* seeds, it was found that treatment T3 (seed soaked in the solution of GA₃@ 300 ppm for 24 hours) shown that it takes minimum days (8.33 days) to sprouting from seeds, which was followed by T2 (10.00 days) and T9 (10.67 days), whereas, maximum days to sprout in the treatment T4 (18.00 days) and T7 (17.00 days)

Table-1 revealed the days for germination in *P. santalinus* seeds, it was found that treatment T3 (seed soaked in the solution of GA₃@ 300 ppm for 24 hours) shown that it takes minimum days (22.67 days) to complete germination from seeds, which was followed by T2 (24.67 days) and T9 (26.67 days) , while maximum days to complete germination in the treatment T12 and T4 i.e. 45.67 days and 44.33 days, respectively.

From table-1, the germination per cent of *P. santalinus* seeds was observed, and found that the treatment T3 (seed soaked in the solution of GA₃@ 300 ppm for 24 hours) shown maximum per cent of germination (71.67%) of seeds, which was followed by T2 (63.33%) and T9 (61.67%) and whereas, lowest germination of seed was found in the treatment T4 and T12 i.e. 31.67 per cent and 28.33 per cent respectively.

Overall parameters of seed germination, among the treatments, seeds soaked in gibberellic acid (GA₃) at 300 ppm for 24 hours (T3) exhibited superior performance. This treatment recorded the earliest emergence at 8.33 days, the minimum duration to final germination at 22.67 days, and the highest germination percentage of 71.67%. This was followed

by treatment T2 (GA₃ at 200 ppm for 24 hours), which showed an emergence at 10.00 days, final germination at 24.67 days, and a germination percentage of 63.33%. In contrast, the control treatment (untreated seeds) recorded the lowest germination percentage, demonstrating the limited natural germination potential of *P. santalinus* seeds due to dormancy.

The enhanced germination observed in GA₃-treated seeds may be attributed to the physiological role of gibberellic acid in breaking seed dormancy. GA₃ is known to activate various cytological and biochemical processes essential for germination. It promotes cell elongation and division by enhancing cell wall flexibility and increasing water uptake. More importantly, GA₃ stimulates the synthesis of hydrolytic enzymes such as amylase, which convert stored starches into soluble sugars, thus providing readily available energy for the growing embryo (Stewart and Freebairn, 1969). Furthermore, GA₃ induces ethylene production, which is known to play a synergistic role in promoting seed germination through the enhancement of enzyme activity and weakening of the endosperm or seed coat.

These findings are consistent with those reported by Patel *et al.* (2018), who observed improved germination in *Pterocarpus santalinus* with GA₃ treatment, and by Thanuja *et al.* (2019) in *Pterocarpus marsupium*, where similar pre-sowing interventions significantly enhanced seed germination performance. The current results reinforce the efficacy of gibberellic acid, particularly at a concentration of 300 ppm, as a practical and reliable treatment for improving germination in *P. santalinus*, a species known for its hard seed coat and physiological dormancy.

Table 1: Effect of pre-sowing seed treatment on germination of *P. santalinus*.

Treatments	Days to emergence (Days)	Days for germination (Days)	Germination (%)
T ₁	13.00	34.33	53.33
T ₂	10.00	24.67	63.33
T ₃	8.33	22.67	71.67
T ₄	18.00	44.33	31.67
T ₅	16.33	39.00	39.33
T ₆	12.00	33.67	60.33
T ₇	17.00	39.67	36.67
T ₈	14.00	38.33	41.67
T ₉	10.67	26.67	61.67
T ₁₀	11.33	29.33	56.67
T ₁₁	13.33	37.00	46.67
T ₁₂	15.67	45.67	28.33
'F' - Test	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(m)±	1.09	2.18	0.46
C.D. at 5%	3.11	6.26	1.33
CV (%)	7.65	5.92	11.05

T₁ :GA₃ @ 100 ppm for 24 hrs, T₂ :GA₃ @ 200 ppm for 24 hrs,
T₃ :GA₃ @ 300 ppm for 24 hrs, T₄ :1% H₂SO₄ for 20 min,
T₅ :3% H₂SO₄ for 20 min., T₆ :5% H₂SO₄ for 20 min,
T₇ :1% HCl for 20 min, T₈ :3% HCl for 20 min,
T₉ :5% HCl for 20 min., T₁₀ :Cow dung slurry (1:1) for 48 hrs,
T₁₁ :Separating seeds from pods with a sharp knife or scalpel and sown directly,
T₁₂ :Control

(A) Pods

(B) Seeds separated from pods

Photo 1: Pods and seeds of *P. santalinus*

Germination Percentage

Fig. 1 Effect of different pre-sowing seed treatments on germination of *P. santalinus*

Conclusion

The findings of the present study indicate that among the twelve pre-sowing seed treatments evaluated, treatment T3 i.e. seeds soaking in gibberellic acid (GA_3) @300 ppm for 24 hours, was the most effective in enhancing germination performance of *Pterocarpus santalinus*. This treatment resulted in the shortest time to emergence and germination, along with the highest germination percentage. These results underscore the significance of pre-sowing treatments, particularly the use of GA_3 , in improving seed germination and promoting successful seedling establishment in this ecologically and economically valuable species.

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